

Exploring the Impact of Affective States on Students' Cognitive Attention During Different Learning Abilities using EEG.

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ABSTRACT : In recent times, there has been a growing interest in utilizing EEG signals to assess students' attention while they engage in various learning activities. When assessing learning abilities, it is important to recognize the intricate relationship between emotions and learning. Emotions play a significant role in shaping students' engagement, motivation, and attention during educational activities. By examining the emotional factors present during learning, we can identify patterns and trends that shed light on students' cognitive processes. This study investigates how affective states, such as sadness and happiness, impact students' attention during different learning tasks, including attention, problem-solving, reasoning, and memory. The present work focused on 20 subjects aged between 21 to 30 years, and EEG signals were collected using the Neurosky Mind wave device. Data analysis was performed using the statistical technique of Mean. Based on the statistical analysis, it was found that during the sad session, girls present the highest level of attention across all activities compared to boys. On the other hand, during the happy session, boys displayed the highest level of attention across all activities compared to girls.

Keywords: Cognitive activities ,Electroencephalography, Mindwave Neurosky

1.INTRODUCTION

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) are communication systems that enable a direct and real-time exchange of information between the brain and the external world.[1] Recent advancements in neuroscience have opened up a promising new avenue for the development of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) that foster greater interaction. These cutting-edge psycho-physiological techniques enable the translation of human neural responses into control signals for computer devices through both hardware and software systems. Remarkably, this technology allows users to communicate using their brain's signals without requiring any physical movement in the

external world [2], [3]. It has several applications such as Medical, Education, Emotion, etc. Emotions are complex phenomena that play significant roles in the quality of human life. Emotion plays a major role in interaction, motivation, perception, cognition process, creativity, attention, learning and decision-making. Within the field of neuroscience, one particularly significant area of study is cognition, which concerns the workings of the human mind. A cognitive state represents the mental process of acquiring knowledge through thoughts, experiences, and sensory inputs. Several processes and functions contribute to cognitive abilities, such as attention, working memory, reasoning, engagement, perception, and problem-solving, among these aspects of cognitive neuroscience, we have focused on the cognitive skill focused attention means all subjects' activities involve active cognitive processes such as problem-solving and critical thinking. So Monitoring the cognitive states of students is particularly useful for applications such as distance learning due to the lack of face to face interactions between the instructor and students.[4]

EEG signals to determine the cognitive state of students as they engaged in various learning activities. Traditional EEG devices are expensive and bulky, making it cumbersome to conduct experimental studies in a non-controlled environment. However, with the rapid advances in sensing technology, new generation of EEG devices that are non-invasive, portable, and affordable have been developed, thus providing an opportunity to conduct measurement studies where the human subjects are immersed in a real-world environment. In this paper, we analyze the impact of affective states such as sad and happy on cognitive attention of students during them performing the different Cognitive based Learning Abilities using Neurosky EEG device.

Keywords: Electroencephalography, Neurosky Mind wave, Cognitive Attention, Learning Activities, Affective states

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews some of the previous works on the different Cognitive states analysis using Brain Computer Based Electroencephalography, at the both National and International levels.

Kavitha P Thomas, A .P .Vinod, [2013] the authors explore the effect of a neurofeedback put together BCI game with respect to the improvement of attention and intellectual abilities of healthy subjects and the trial aftereffects of this examination show that the proposed neurofeedback preparing model starts the player to extend his entropy scores, upgrade attention level and achieve higher focuses in the game.

Geeta U .Navalyal, Rahul D .Gavas, [2014], point of this investigation is to detail a technique with the assistance of Brain Computer Interface game to help the coaches in noticing and

assessing the attention levels of the students ,at normal intervals during the preparation time frame. For this examination reason the gaming climate is planned utilizing Open Source Graphics Library (OpenGL) package and the game control is through the cerebrum waves of player's utilizing the Brain Computer Interface (BCI) innovation.

Poulami Ghosh ,Ankita Mazumder et.al [2015] the target of this investigation was to assess the cognitive state of brain. They concentrated in on memory and attention state. For this classification purpose they used Support Vector Machine and they acquired 79% classification precision.

Xiaowei Li ,Martyn Ratcliffe et .al.,[2015]describe Real-time EEG – based BCI framework which estimates attention level. In this investigation they contrast their methodology and conventional methodologies, three consideration levels were ordered by a KNN classifier dependent on the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) model.

KHIMTOA , kok SWEE SIM [2015] In this paper they constructed the relationship between EEG and attention level. This study aims to introduce a more effective learning algorithm to measure the attention level using EEG. Studied monitoring using experiment with webcam and eye tracking algorithm using EMOTIVE instrument which records electrodes. Since our study is about brain responses in attentive and inattentive behaviour analysis only electrodes in frontal cortex(AF3 &AF4) and parietal cortex (PZ) are used, with the help of deep learning model like (AMNN,RNN,CNN &LSTM).

Ng Wei Bin, Saidatul Ardeenawatie Awang ,et.al ,[2019] The aim of this paper was to determine the informative EEG channel/s and brain region for typing activity. 20 healthy with right-handed subjects from Universiti Malaysia Perlis (UniMAP) were enrolled in this study. Typing task was performed for 3 trials and 5 minutes per trial. In EEG signal processing, Notch filter and Butterworth bandpass filter were used to remove powerline artefact and to filter the signal into alpha (8-13Hz) and beta waves (13-30Hz). Welch method was applied to extract features from typing task. The obtained results were then undergoing the statistical analysis before load into the K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) classifier.They found that channel P3 in parietal region and channel T6 in temporal region give highest accuracy which was 99.44% for typing task activity.

Dan Ni, Shuo Wang and Guocheng liu , [2020]This paper has made empirical case study on differences in learner's attention when using different three learning media. EEG technology used to measure mobile learning attention and process them to determine learners learning and memory during learning and cognitive load. Also pointed learning style in mobile learning which could access by learners from anytime any place in any form. Founded that attention value in both male and female have a higher attention of text media.

Sarwar Marshad , Md. Rabiuzzaman Mazumder , et.al , [2020]In this research paper they used Neurosky mindwave2 is a mobile lightweight and low cost EEG device it is mainly used for education and research work. This device also gives attention, meditation and eye blinking. Neurosky mind wave mobile 2 is possible implementation error by doing preprocessing in the device. In data analysis they controlled and collected data were divided into groups according to the age at 10-20 and above 29 & also men and women. They got six types of data are alpha, beta, gamma, attention, meditation, eye blinking from Neurosky mind wave mobile 2. They shows the

mean, threshold level and attention, mediation and eye blink also according to age group over men and women.

In 2021, Jesus G. Cruz-Garza, Michael Darfler, James D. Rounds, and their colleagues conducted a study to explore how exposure to different virtual learning environments, featuring varying window placement and room dimensions, affects neuronal dynamics. Participants engaged in five short cognitive tasks, including the Stroop Test, Digit Span Test, Benton Test, Visual Memory Test, and arithmetical test, across various design conditions. The researchers analyzed the cognitive test results and collected Electroencephalogram (EEG) data from multiple classroom design scenarios. The study did not find any significant changes in cognitive test performance associated with the architectural design elements being investigated. However, the researchers utilized EEG analysis to identify brain patterns related to environmental factors. Notably, the bilateral occipital, parietal, and frontal regions in the theta (4–8 Hz) and alpha (8–12 Hz) frequency bands exhibited the most distinctive EEG characteristics in response to the different virtual learning environments.

Andrea Apicella, Pasquale Arpaia Mirco Frosolone, et al., [2022]

The authors propose an individualized wearable system that utilizes EEG to detect engagement within the context of Learning 4.0. This system's effectiveness is assessed by measuring its classification accuracy in predicting levels of engagement. The main goal of the system is to automate teaching platforms and customize them for each user by identifying declines in cognitive and emotional engagement. The success of the learning process greatly depends on the learner's level of engagement. When signs of distraction, disinterest, or superficial participation are detected, the teaching strategy can be personalized by automatically adjusting content and communication methods. To validate the system, an experimental case study was conducted involving twenty-one students. The participants were given a task to learn how a specific human-machine interface works, which required both cognitive and motor skills. Standard stimuli, including a cognitive task (Continuous Performance Test), music background (Music Emotion Recognition - MER database), and social feedback (Hermans and De Houwer database), were used to establish a reliable reference for engagement. Using a within-subject approach, the signal processing pipeline, which consisted of Filter bank, Common Spatial Pattern, and Support Vector Machine techniques, achieved an average accuracy of approximately 77% in detecting both cognitive and emotional engagement.

3.DATABASE CREATION AND SIGNAL ACQUISITION

A. Participants

For this proposed experiment, the data has been collected from 20 (10 Male, 10 Female) postgraduate students participants from the Department of Computer Science and IT, Dr B.A.M.University, Aurangabad. Participants' ages were between 21 to 30 years. Detailed information for all participants in table 2, all volunteers gave their written consent prior to participating, in accordance with the relevant guidelines and the principles. All had normal or

and none of them had any known history of epilepsy, migraine or any other neurological condition. Additionally, the participants received prior training and followed the guidelines provided by the researcher.

Table no.1 .Details of Participants

Subject. No.	Age	Gender	Nationality	Device Type
Subject 1	22	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 2	26	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 3	23	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 4	22	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 5	22	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 6	22	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 7	24	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 8	30	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 9	26	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 10	22	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 11	23	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 12	24	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 13	26	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 14	24	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 15	23	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 16	22	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 17	21	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 18	29	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 19	23	M	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave
Subject 20	28	F	Indian	Neurosky Mind wave

B.Data Acquisition

In this work, An BCI-based Neurosky Mindwave device was used for Data acquisition of brain signals. Neurosky Mindwave Mobile II is a low-cost, user-friendly wireless EEG device with 512 Hz sampling rate .However, it is a single-channel BCI headset, giving super mobility during the usage time. The Mind Wave Mobile 2 safely measures and outputs the EEG power spectrums (alpha waves, beta waves, etc). For this device's connection with the computer / Mobile , we first need to turn on Bluetooth on both devices and then pair them. After pairing them Neurosky headset should be worn properly in the head. It's one probe must be on a hairy scalp. And another is in the earlobe. EEG is an android application that is connected to the Neurosky Mindwave device. The readings obtained from the Mind wave device are recorded and delivered through email by this application. The raw data is in CSV or excel format for further evaluation. The workspace where we experimented was completely quiet and had no external Disturbances.

Figure 01 :Data Acquisition using eegID application

C.Procedure

In this study, we focused on affective states , such as happiness and sadness, as well as cognitive state including Attention, for analyzing the impact of affective states on cognitive attention in relation to different Learning abilities. Each subject was provided with information about the experiment and given a consent form to read and sign. After reading and signing the consent form, Participants were asked to calm and relax for get used to the learning environment. After this participants were shown video stimuli related to sad emotions for a duration of 4 to 7 minutes. Subsequently, they were given tasks related to attention, problem-solving, reasoning, and memory activities, all within a limited time period. We conducted three sessions for each activity.

After completing the first task, participants were once again shown video stimuli related to happiness, and the same procedure as mentioned in the first step was repeated. In total, we obtained 24 records from both tasks.(3 session of each activity= $3*4= 12$ for each task) In order to generalize the data acquired during this session, participants were requested to remain Relax and calm. After the completion of the both task, subjects were asked to fill the questionnaire about the experiment.

4. EXPERIMENTAL REPRESENTATION

The collected data was categorized based on activities and gender into two groups. The Attention and Meditation data were divided by 100, as they were already scaled between 0 and 100 by the headset. These data were approximately normally distributed and plotted as received from the headset. From the Neurosky Mind wave Mobile II, we obtained six types of data (Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Attention, Meditation, Eye blink), but only the Attention values were used for this particular experiment, as cognitive attention was the focus of our research.

Statistical parameters, particularly the Mean value, were considered for analysis. We calculated the average of all three sessions of each subject for all activities, and for the final comparison analysis, we again took the average of each activity. For the cognitive attention analysis based on affective states, we specifically considered sad and happy states. We choose four different cognitive-based learning activities: attention, mathematical problem-solving, reasoning, and memory activities. The study was focused on M.Sc. students, both girls and boys, from different age groups.

In the following sections, we presented graphical representations of all the statistical analysis based on our study observations and considerations. Firstly, we compared the cognitive attention of girls and boys during the Sad and Happy sessions, as illustrated in figure 2 and figure 3.

Figure 2: Comparison of All subjects During Sad Session

Figure 3: Comparison of All subjects During Happy Session

Then, we proceeded with the second observation, which involved comparing the Mean Attention values of girls and boys during the sad session shown in Figure 4 and the happy session in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Mean result of girls and boys in sad sessions for all activities

Figure 5 :Mean result of girls and boys in Happy sessions for all activities.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we analyzed the attention from the EEG experiment and answered the following questions:

- 1) Did boys show any differences in their attention across four activities, namely Attention, Problem Solving, Reasoning, and Memory, during the Sad session?
- 2) Were there differences in the girls' attention across four activities, namely Attention, Problem Solving, Reasoning, and Memory, during the Happy session?
- 3) Were there any differences in the attention of boys and girls across four activities, including Attention, Problem Solving, Reasoning, and Memory, during the Sad session?
- 4) Were there variations in the attention of boys and girls during the Happy session in relation to four activities: Attention, Problem Solving, Reasoning, and Memory?

1) Did boys exhibit differences in their attention across four activities, namely Attention, Problem Solving, Reasoning, and Memory, during the Sad session? Based on the results, it was observed that the average attention value for the reasoning activity ($M=53.67$) was higher than the other activities, including attention ($M=51.50$), problem-solving ($M=49.54$), and memory ($M=46.33$).

2)Whereas average attention value of the attention activity in Boys (M=53.70)is greater than the problem solving ,reasoning and memory activities. It could be seen that there was no significant difference in the attention of above learning activities during the happy session and the attention of attention activity showed a higher mean, which could prove that the impact of happy stimuli had a certain promotion effect on the attention of the learners.

3)Also Average attention of memory (M=56.80) and reasoning(M=54.94) is greater than the other activities during sad session in girls and Average attention of reasoning (M=50.10) is slightly greater than the other activities during happy session in girls.

4) During the Sad session, the mean attention of all activities showed no significant differences between girls and boys. However, during the happy session, the mean attention values for the attention and reasoning activities were somewhat similar between girls and boys, while these values differed from the activities of problem solving and memory.

Conclusion: In conclusion, this study aimed to investigate the influence of emotional factors on students' cognitive attention during different learning abilities using Neurosky technology. The findings indicate that considering emotional factors during the learning process can significantly enhance the examination of students' cognitive states, including attention and learning abilities. By analyzing the impact of emotions on students' learning experiences, this study provides valuable insights into how different emotional factors affect their ability to acquire and retain knowledge. The comprehensive analysis incorporated various emotional states, such as sadness and happiness, along with different learning activities, including attention, problem-solving, reasoning, and memory. The results obtained through the statistical Mean technique revealed interesting trends. During the Sad session, the mean attention of all activities showed no significant differences between girls and boys. However, during the happy session, the mean attention values for attention and reasoning activities were somewhat similar between girls and boys. In light of these findings, it becomes evident that examining students' cognitive attention in the context of emotional factors during the learning process can lead to a more comprehensive understanding of their abilities. Moreover, considering emotional factors allows for the identification of patterns, enabling tailored interventions and the creation of a more conducive learning environment. Ultimately, this approach can help students improve both their cognitive and emotional states, fostering more effective learning experiences. Overall, this study highlights the importance of recognizing emotional factors in the educational setting and its potential implications for enhancing students' learning outcomes. Further research in this area can continue to shed light on the complex interplay between emotions and cognition, providing valuable knowledge for educational practitioners.

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